

THE DESIGN OF A BINDER FOR EARTH STABILIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Hemihydrate, lime, and natural pozzolan have been used, individually or in binary mixtures, as stabilizers in vernacular architecture. Nowadays, however, earth stabilization is usually done with Portland cement at a high environmental cost. In this paper, we revisit vernacular stabilizers by investigating the hydration mechanisms of a ternary binder made of natural pozzolan (trass), lime, and gypsum. Aiming at developing a binder formulation suitable for earth stabilization, we show that enhanced compressive strength and minimum carbon footprint can be obtained when we tackle the hydration reactions and maximize the fraction of low-carbon materials.

KEYWORDS

Earth Construction; Natural Pozzolan; Binder Formulation; Hydration products; Ettringite.

INTRODUCTION

Over the last 200 years, human activities have disturbed ecosystems on such a global scale that the effects of human interventions can be used to characterize a new geologic epoch, the Anthropocene. As other intervals in the geologic time scale, the Anthropocene epoch is characterized by mass extinction and by a characteristic stratigraphic level that enables its recognition by the presence of materials such as ceramic bricks, plastics, and concrete (Hazen, Grew, Origlieri, & Downs, 2017; Waters et al., 2016). Not only it is a prominent signal of our geological epoch concrete is also a great contributor to climate change due to its large-scale use (Monteiro, Miller, & Horvath, 2017).

Today, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) urges decision-makers to take urgent action to drastically reduce greenhouse gas emissions. A 50 % reduction is required in the next 10 years if climate neutrality is to be reached between 2040 and 2050 (IPCC, 2018). The construction industry, due to its high contribution, has to take its share (Habert et al., 2020). Recent studies show that cement emissions can be reduced by 50 % by implementing existing solutions and efficiency optimization along the entire value chain from cement and concrete producers down to architects and end-users (Habert et al., 2020). However, the remaining 50 % seems more difficult to avoid as this would require massive implementation of carbon capture, storage, and use facilities associated with very significant financial, energy and time resources (Nick & Thalmann, 2021). Alternatives to cement seem therefore crucial to explore. Timber is usually brought forward as a low-carbon construction alternative. However, recent studies show that forest locations do not correspond to the locations where mass urbanization takes place (Pomponi, Hart, Arehart, & D'Amico, 2020). In short, major forests are located in the global North, where most of the building stock has already been built. Rapid urbanization is happening in South East Asia or Africa, where the remaining tropical forest should be preserved.

Another alternative could be earth-based construction. Earth (soil) is a widely abundant material, particularly in urban environments where large volumes of excavation materials are generated by

nearly every construction site. Earth has also been used as a vernacular construction material all over the globe for more than 10,000 years. However, low compressive strength and sensitivity to water make this material less attractive for modern constructions, unless it is stabilized (Van Damme & Houben, 2018). To improve strength, resistance to disaggregation, and erosion, Portland cement (PC) is the most obvious choice for earth stabilization nowadays, despite the numerous historical examples of the use of other mineral binders as stabilizers in vernacular construction, some of which are cited in Figure 1. However, the outstanding environmental performance of earth materials fades out when PC is incorporated even in low amounts (5-10 %) (Van Damme & Houben, 2018).

Figure 1. Examples of the use of natural pozzolan, lime, and gypsum in vernacular construction. (Ahmad Bany Yaseen, Al-Amoush, Al-Farajat, & Mayyas, 2013; Aprea, 2018; Artioli, Secco, & Addis, 2019; Dobias, Vokac, & Pokorný, 2017; Fort, Ergenç, Aly, Alvarez de Buergo, & Hemedda, 2021; Jackson et al., 2014; Kumar, 2003; López et al., 2011; Morsy, Alsayed, & Salloum, 2012; Morsy, Rashad, Shoukry, Mokhtar, & El-Khodary, 2020; Pekmezci, Kafescouclu, & Agahzadeh, 2012; Shen, Zhou, & Zhao, 2007; Society of American Military Engineers, 1919; Vimmrová, Keppert, Michalko, & Černý, 2014).

In lime-pozzolan binders, the hardening mechanisms are typically hydration and carbonation and they have different reaction kinetics. Hydration – the consumption of lime by pozzolanic reactions – usually precedes the carbonation of lime, except for pozzolanic materials that react only to a very limited extent or too slowly. In that case, the consumption of lime by carbonation may be favoured. However, both take place at rates lower than that of PC, which results in the gradual development of properties mainly during the first 2-3 months (Alvarez et al., 2021). While the progress of those two mechanisms is largely influenced by the mixing water ratio and the curing conditions, factors affecting the reactivity of the pozzolan, i.e., specific surface area and amorphous content, play a preponderant role in the enhancement of hydration reactions. In that context, pretreatments that aim at enhancing the reactivity of slowly reacting materials by means of chemical, mechanical, or thermal activation are often utilized. Nevertheless, the widely proposed use of chemical activators, intense milling, calcination, and high-temperature curing (Ali & Jaleh, 2006; Shi & Day, 2001) may come along with a decrease in the environmental performance of the binders, since some activation strategies can be highly energy-intensive (Shi, 2001).

The use of stabilizers that have a low carbon footprint is required if earth materials are to be used under conditions that require stabilization, such as masonry blocks for exterior walls. Moreover, a considerable strength gain within the first 28 curing days is desired by current construction practices. In this work, focusing on earth stabilization with mineral binders, we revisit stabilizers that have been historically used alone or in binary combinations and propose a new ternary binder based on three components: a natural pozzolan, lime, and gypsum. The natural pozzolan used in this study, trass, is a volcanic tuff from the region of the Vulkaneifel in Rhineland, Germany, which has been used in

mixtures with lime and aggregates on several occasions throughout history to produce mortars and concrete (Aprea, 2018; Society of American Military Engineers, 1919). Here, we explore the hydration mechanisms of the binder and investigate its mechanical and environmental performance while developing formulations that are optimized in terms of hydration products, compressive strength, and carbon footprint.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used to produce the binder are a natural pozzolan – trass (Tubag, Germany), calcium hydroxide $\geq 96\%$ (Sigma-Aldrich), calcium sulfate dihydrate $\geq 98\%$ (gypsum), calcium sulfate hemihydrate $\geq 97\%$ (plaster of Paris) from Acros Organics, and sucrose $\geq 99.5\%$ (Sigma-Aldrich). The natural pozzolan was used as received, without further mechanical or thermal treatment. Its amorphous content (49%) was estimated using the internal standard method (with corundum) by X-ray diffraction (XRD).

The formation of hydration products was studied by XRD in binder pastes hydrated for 28 days at room temperature. A Bragg-Brentano X-ray diffractometer (D8 Advance, Bruker AXS, Germany) with $\text{CoK}\alpha$ radiation (1.78901 Å) was used. The simplified chemical composition of the anhydrous binders is plotted in Figure 2 in terms of CaO , SO_3 , and Al_2O_3 . Thermodynamic modelling of phase assemblage was also used to study the hydration of the binder. The calculations were carried out using GEMS software package and the PSI-Nagra and CEMDATA18 databases (Lothenbach et al., 2019).

Figure 2. Simplified chemical composition of the different binder formulations evaluated in this study. T/P stands for the mass ratio between trass and plaster of Paris (hemihydrate).

Furthermore, earth mixtures containing 30 wt.% of a mineral earth material for plastering (Stroba Naturbaustoffe, Switzerland) and 70 wt.% of standard mortar sand (complying with EN 196-1) stabilized with 20.5 wt.% of binder (of dry solids) were used to evaluate the impact of different binder formulations on the compressive strength of room temperature-cured stabilized earth specimens (40x40x160 mm). In both binder pastes and stabilized earth mixtures the water:binder ratio was 0.98 and the lime content was fixed to 12.2 wt.% of the binder.

The simplified calculation of the environmental performance of the mix designs was done in terms of the global warming potential (GWP) in $\text{kg CO}_2\text{-eq/kg}$ of binder, calculated using IPCC 2013 impact assessment method, where life cycle inventory was collected through Ecoinvent v3.8 database.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Formation of hydration products

Part of the diffraction patterns of the binder pastes hydrated for 28 days is shown in Figure 3 (a), highlighting that the crystalline hydration products formed as a result of the reaction between the

binder components – trass, gypsum, and lime – are ettringite ($\text{Ca}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3(\text{OH})_{12}\cdot 26\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). Gypsum formation is a consequence of the rehydration of hemihydrate and it is still abundant after 28 days in the binder mixes that contain a large fraction of hemihydrate (T/P 0.38 and T/P 1.25). On the contrary, gypsum is fully reacted in the binder mix that contains the largest fraction of trass (T/P 8.00). In that binder formulation, higher amounts of ettringite are observed as a result of the improved balance between the original sulfate source (hemihydrate) and the aluminosilicate source (trass) in the binder. The large fraction of trass enhances the availability of reactive alumina that is needed for ettringite formation. Moreover, thermodynamic modelling of phase assemblage, shown in Figure 3 (b) showed that, in addition to ettringite and gypsum, considerable amounts of C-(A)-S-H is also predicted to form as a result of the hydration of the binder. Higher contents of C-(A)-S-H are predicted to form in the binder formulations that contain a larger fraction of trass. The typically poorly crystalline nature of C-(A)-S-H makes its individual identification and quantification by XRD difficult when other amorphous phases are present in the sample, which is the case of the amorphous fraction of the partially reacted trass.

Figure 3. (a) XRD patterns (Co-K α) of binder mixes hydrated for 28 days and (b) Mass of C-(A)-S-H and ettringite formed during hydration of different binder formulations, as indicated by the trass:plaster of Paris (T/P) mass ratio. The values were obtained by thermodynamic modelling assuming that the degree of hydration of the reactive fraction of trass is 20 %.

Mechanical and environmental performance

The evaluation of the mechanical and environmental performance of the binder was done based on its eco-performance, defined as the ratio between the compressive strength of the stabilized earth mixtures measured after curing for 28 days and the carbon footprint of the binder formulation used in the stabilization. In addition to the mixes evaluated in the previous section, additional binder formulations were included in the analysis: a formulation in which hemihydrate was replaced with uncalcined gypsum (T/G 8.0), a formulation containing uncalcined gypsum and sucrose addition (sucrose was added in the mixing water as 0.1 wt.% of the binder; T/G 8.0 + 0.1%S), two trass-lime formulations (trass 78% - lime 22% and trass 55% - lime 45%), a trass-cement formulation (trass 55% - PC 45%), and a reference data point that corresponds to unstabilized raw earth. The eco-performances of all described materials are plotted in Figure 4 as a function of the compressive strength of the mixes.

The points shown in the bottom half of Figure 4 are examples of the inefficient use of mineral binders in earth stabilization. The use of such stabilization techniques contributes to a modest increase in the strength of earth materials but their eco-performance is significantly lower than that of unstabilized earth. Looking closer to the trass-lime binder formulations, a change from trass 78% - lime 22% – which has proportions of binder components close to that of T/P 8.0, but without hemihydrate – to trass 55% - lime 45% – composition found in commercially available trass-lime ready mixes – is

marked by an increase in strength, however, the eco-performance is maintained because the strength enhancement came with an increase in the carbon footprint of the binder since it contains a larger fraction of lime. Moreover, overall, both formulations are still characterized by low mechanical performance (compressive strength in the 2-3 MPa range). That is also the case for the T/P 1.25 formulation, which contains a high hemihydrate fraction. Only a marginal contribution to strength is obtained and this contribution is environmentally costly, since the relative proportions of binder components – trass and hemihydrate – are far from optimum. This shows that the mere addition of hemihydrate to a trass-lime binder, without careful binder design, may not further enhance mechanical performance.

Figure 4. Eco-performance of the binders explored in this study (data points represented in shades of green) compared to other earth stabilization techniques (data points in shades of red) and non-stabilized earth (data point represented in blue). The descriptions of binder formulations are given in terms of the trass:plaster of Paris (T/P) or trass:gypsum (T/G) mass ratios for the formulations investigated in this study, and in wt.% of the binder in the case of the additional data points. The compressive strength of all materials (except the non-stabilized earth, which contained no binder) was measured in earth mixtures stabilized with the same binder content (20.5 %wt. of dry solids) cured for 28 days at room temperature. The data is from this study.

By understanding the hydration mechanisms of the trass-lime-hemihydrate binder, we observed that improved formulations (in terms of hydration products) were obtained with an increase in the aluminosilicate content. This change in binder composition, visible in Figure 2, resulted in the enhancement of the formation of desirable hydration products i.e., ettringite and C-(A)-S-H, as shown by XRD and thermodynamic modelling. Here we observe that such formulations perform better also in terms of mechanical and environmental performance. With an increase in the fraction of trass, the (green) data points start to accumulate on the upper right side of Figure 4, which corresponds to a zone of higher strength and higher eco-performance. Nevertheless, it is interesting to note that the use of uncalcined gypsum instead of hemihydrate results in a decrease in strength and eco-performance of the binder, despite the lower environmental impact of the former. However, the addition of a small (0.1 wt.% binder) sucrose dosage elevates the compressive strength of the T/G 8.0 mix to an extent that the calculated eco-performance of that formulation becomes higher than that of T/P 8.0 and closer to that of raw earth. Therefore, the improved formulations obtained in this study are able to provide sufficient strength to raw earth (over 6 MPa) at a very low environmental cost.

The low environmental impact of such formulations, which is partially responsible for the observed eco-performance values, is a result of the use of a large fraction of trass, a minimally processed

material. The use of other low-carbon reactive aluminosilicate materials i.e., industrial or agricultural wastes that do not require energy-intensive activation treatments before their implementation as binder components is expected to result in similarly high eco-performance.

Having a closer look at the material use and carbon footprint of mix designs stabilized with the T/G 8.0 + 0.1%S formulation, we observe that, despite having a low mass fraction in the binder, lime is the material responsible for the largest share in the CO₂ emissions from the entire mix design. That is a result of the energy-intensive processes employed during the production of lime. Despite having calcination temperature below that of PC, the production of lime still relies on the decarbonation of limestone (CaCO₃) at temperatures around 900 °C. The other binder components, however, – gypsum, the natural pozzolan (trass), and the additive (sucrose) – have negligible CO₂ emissions.

The environmental cost of the stabilization technique proposed in this study can be further reduced through the production of stabilized earth mixtures containing less than 20.5% binder. If only 5 % of the same binder formulation is used, the lime content drops to 0.6 % (of dry solids), and the CO₂ footprint of the mix design falls below 1 kg CO_{2eq}/kg of material. Nevertheless, the compressive strength is expected to be significantly lower than the one reached by the mix design stabilized with 20.5 % binder (6 MPa).

CONCLUSIONS

- A ternary binder inspired by vernacular earth stabilization with natural pozzolan (trass), lime, and gypsum was developed.
- The main hydration products (based on XRD and thermodynamic modelling data) are ettringite, C-(A)-S-H, and gypsum.
- By increasing the fraction of trass in the binder, we obtained a formulation that produced higher amounts of desirable hydration products (ettringite and C-(A)-S-H), reached higher compressive strength at 28 days, and enhanced the environmental performance. Therefore, the enhancement of the hydration reactions was done by increasing the fraction of the slowly reacting material – trass – rather than using energy-intensive activation methods.
- Despite the low lime content in the binder, the carbon footprint of this binder component represents the largest CO₂ share within the mix design.
- If the improved formulations are to be used in earth stabilization, we showed that an earth material stabilized with 20.5 wt.% binder (of dry solids) can reach compressive strength values over 6MPa with only 2.5 wt.% of calcined material (lime).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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